

COMMUNITY POLICING – START EXPERIENCE MINISTRY OF INTERIOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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Abstract

Community policing, as a model of police organization and operational practice, emerged from a critical assessment of traditional policing approaches. Its goal is to create a modern, responsive police institution that meets the needs of democratic societies and aligns with international and European standards (Skolnick & Bayley, 1988; European Commission, 2020). The concept emphasizes preventive and problem-solving approaches, partnerships with local communities, respect for human and minority rights, civil liberties, equality, and multicultural coexistence (Cordner, 2021; Lum & Koper, 2020).

In the Republic of Serbia, community policing has been adopted as a global model for police organization and operations, reflecting the principle that the police serve society, protect its members, and promote ethical and cultural values. The strategic vision of the Ministry of Interior of Serbia is to develop a modern, professional, and accountable police service capable of responding effectively to contemporary societal challenges while maintaining alignment with European and international standards. This paper examines the conceptual foundations and organizational implications of community policing as a framework for modern democratic policing.

Keywords: *community policing, police, organization, European Union, Ministry of Interior.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Community policing, as a new model of police organization, began to be applied in the United States of America in the early 1980s and later developed in Western European countries (Great Britain, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, the Netherlands, France, Germany), some Asian countries (Hong Kong, Japan), as well as Canada and Australia. Since 2000, community policing has also been implemented in post-communist countries of Eastern Europe that are in a transition period.

This approach is based on respect for human rights, responsibility, and the need to carry out effective police operations in partnership with communities for which police perform public service. This philosophy focuses on the community – the public – and its

needs, as well as on the fact that the police serve the community in a responsible manner and through respect for human rights.

At the beginning of the new millennium, the Republic of Serbia embarked on the path of transition and long-awaited social reforms, emphasizing the necessity of democratization, the construction of a modern state, and the rule of law (Nikač, 2019). The reform of the police *de facto* began with the separation of the former State Security Service from the *RS MOI* and the establishment of the Security Information Agency (BIA) as a specialized agency (secret service) for the protection of the constitutional order. The remaining (mostly) part of the *RS MOI* – the former Public Security Service and the accompanying logistics service – was programmatically shaped through an official document entitled *Vision for the Reform of RS MOI*, according to which the most important objectives of the transformation of the police are depolitization, decriminalization, professionalization, modern (pro-European) organization, and the rule of law, among others. (Vision and Policy Mission, 2002).

De iure, the reform of the *RS MOI* was articulated through the Law on Police of the RS, which highlighted the concept of the organization of the civil province, at the center of which is the Police Directorate. Within the structure of the Police Directorate, according to the hierarchical principle, there are functional lines of work (administration) and territorial organizational units (PD Belgrade, RPD, PS). (Law on Police, 2018). The new organizational model of the *RS MOI* (“citizen service”) also implied a new way of police work; therefore, based on a critical analysis of the previous traditional (repressive) system, the concept of police work in the community was adopted as a pilot project.

2. THE CONCEPT OF COMMUNITY POLICING

In modern doctrine and practice, the concept of *community policing* is not uniquely and uniformly defined; rather, depending on the author and the field of study, there are several different definitions, with many similar but also differing elements.

According to Skolnick and Bayley (1988), community policing, in the performance of its tasks, is based on the following principles: (a) planned, developed, and two-way active relations between the police and citizens, with due respect for local problems and community needs; (b) territorial decentralization of the police, including police stations, substations, and other forms of localized presence; (c) reorientation of patrol activities toward preventive and problem-solving functions; and (d) the introduction and increased involvement of civilian personnel in police work (Skolnick & Bayley, 1988). *Recent comparative research highlights the multidimensional and context-specific nature of community policing and its evolving practices in European environments* (Bayerl et al., 2017; de Maillard & Terpstra, 2021).

According to a second group of authors led by Willard, who worked within the *Community Policing Consortium project*, the concept of community police includes community partnership and problem solving. The first component highlights the development of police relations with the community, involvement in crime prevention, and the pooling of resources in accordance with community needs. The second component includes the identification of community problems and ways of solving them (Zekavica, 2005, p.83-89).

We are of the opinion that the definition of community policing given by the American theorists Trojanovicz and Bucqueroux can be accepted, according to which it is a concept that expresses a new philosophy of police work, based on the idea that the police and citizens work together and use different creative ways to solve problems at the level of

the local community related to crime, fear of crime, and other social disorders(Trojanovicz&Bucqueroux,1990).

3. ELEMENTS OF COMMUNITY POLICING

The elements of the concept of *community policing* are numerous and generally identical in most organizational forms and models; however, their importance is particularly emphasized through partnership with the community and problem-oriented police work.

Partnership is a category based on the equality of the community, the police, and other entities that participate in the process of resolving security and related problems in society. On this basis, cooperation is further developed through communication, identification, and resolution of the problems of the participants in the process, namely the police, institutions, local governments, organizations, the business community, and citizens. The police and their partners must work together because security and crime problems in the community significantly affect the quality of life of citizens and are never completely under the control of the police and other community bodies. For these reasons, the joint work of the police and other actors is necessary to solve problems that the police organization alone cannot solve. In this sense, the police and the community pool resources and work to find solutions to eliminate, mitigate and prevent the consequences of actions, conflicts and potential problems (Simić,2009).

The principles on which partnerships between the police and the community are developed are as follows: equality (reciprocal respect, freedom of decision-making, creativity, equality in joint work, and valuation of contributions, etc.); trust (fulfillment of commitments made by the police and meeting the expectations to the public and partners); problem solving (in a persistent and consistent manner); and joint responsibility (shared responsibility of the police and the community for cooperation, planned activities, and implemented measures in the realization of security)(Simonović, 2006).

Problem-oriented police work involves interactive and joint action by the police and society in identifying and resolving problems. According to Goldstein, this approach is based on the study of specific community problems, including the analysis of local security issues (e.g., extortion, prostitution, juvenile delinquency), citizens' expectations, and appropriate means of response(Goldstein, 1979). In recent years, research on evidence-based policing has further reinforced the importance of combining these community-oriented approaches with data-driven decision-making and problem-solving strategies (Koper et al., 2025), demonstrating the evolution of problem-oriented policing in contemporary practice.

Problem-oriented police work include the following elements: a standard operational model of work (as opposed to ad hoc responses to individual cases); the involvement of police officers from all areas of work (not only specialists and managers); cooperation between the police and other entities (agencies, services); the influence, participation, and responsibility of the community; and problem solving. Community-oriented police activity is not a static program but is a guiding philosophy that seeks to meet the needs of the community through a high level of professionalism and continuous development.

4. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF COMMUNITY POLICING

Based on the outlined concept and elements of community policing, both doctrine and practice largely define and determine the basic principles on which the concept, organization and work of community policing are founded. In our opinion, the basic principles of community policing can be conditionally grouped according to: social environmental factors (changes, reforms), the police and its role (leadership, mission, powers, responsibility), functions (vision, services, problem solving), and mutual relationships (partnership, cooperation, equality, trust) etc. We will briefly consider the most important basic principles of community policing related to the objective and subjective circumstances on the one hand, and personal and functional elements on the other.

According to the concepts of a large number of authors and police experts, the most important basic principles of community policing include:

- Change –creating new partnerships with the community and changes within the police that increase opportunity for all participants to contribute to building community capacity and jointly solving community problems;
- Leadership – implying continuous emphasis on and strengthening of the vision, values, and mission of the police within the local community, at all organizational levels. Every police officer must demonstrate initiative, within their capabilities and competencies, to influence others and promote the philosophy of community policing;
- Vision –representing the image of the ideal, i.e., the way in which public safety and quality of life are to be enhanced through community policing;
- Partnership –the development of partnership among all community groups as a means of promoting cooperation and consensus. Cooperation represents both a philosophy and a strategy through which the police develop community capacity and solve problems;
- Problem solving – an analytical process and strategic approach aimed at identifying and accurately recognizing phenomena and events in the community and their causes, in order to design appropriate solutions and strategies;
- Equality – implies that the police provide services to all citizens regardless of race, gender, nationality, religious affiliation, material status, sexual orientation, or other differences;
- Trust–representing the belief that the police genuinely act in accordance with what they communicate to the public;
- Empowerment – implying greater freedom in decision-making for police officers and citizens;
- Service – reflecting the commitment of community policing to provide decentralized and personalized service of an intensity and type determined by community needs;
- Responsibility –referring to the shared responsibility of the police and the community for security outcomes.

5. COMMUNITY POLICING IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

The social basis for the development of the concept of community policing in the Republic of Serbia lies in the fact that, at the end of the last century, significant social changes occurred, after which public institutions entered a reform process and began participating in the construction of democratic values with the support of civil society. Among these institutions is the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Serbia and the police as the institution most directly responsible for law enforcement and security protection. The issue of security should be interpreted broadly, in the sense that, in addition to the police, interested and responsible citizens, other authorities, and community entities are involved, because security also encompasses a subjective sense of safety and a general consensus within the community.

In the context of the social environment, the police in the Republic of Serbia took into account the legacy of the past, previous relations and communication with citizens, the need for the development of democratic governance, requirements for organizational reform, orientation towards citizens' needs, and the enhancement of security in order to reduce fear of crime. On this basis, it was envisaged that the *RS MOI* and the police would be transformed into a modern police service capable of adapting its organization and activities to citizens' needs. (Vision and Mission, 2002).

The normative and legal basis for the development of community policing in the Republic of Serbia was established with the adoption of the Law on Police at the end of 2005, grounded in domestic police-legal practice, traditions, experience, and international standards (Law on Police, 2005). Following the adoption of the Law on the Security Information Agency and the separation of the State Security Service from the former *RS MOI*, the most significant novelties of the Law on Police related to the concept and systematization of public security activities into classical police functions.

The most important innovations introduced by the Law on Police concern the organization, powers, and control of police work. In a systemic and legal sense, the police formally acquired the status of a public service operating in the service of citizens, in accordance with reform-oriented commitments and regional and international documents stating that "the police force represents a public service created by law, which must be responsible for maintaining and enforcing the law" (Resolution, 1979). This broader framework is further reflected in the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the European Code of Police Ethics, and other instruments relevant to the democratic development of policing.

According to the Law on Police, the basic duty of the police is to ensure the safety of all persons within the territory of the Republic of Serbia. This includes providing protection of rights and freedoms, eliminating danger, performing rescue functions, assuming responsibility for failures, informing the public both directly and indirectly, cooperating with citizens and organized groups in the interest of public safety, and continuously protecting human life and security. Accordingly, the objective of police work is the equal protection of security, rights, and freedoms, the application of the law, and the strengthening of the rule of law, in compliance with national and international standards of police conduct.

Police powers are regulated in a manner that emphasizes the protection of the rights of persons subjected to police action, openness towards the public, humanity, proportionality, and effective legal protection. This legal framework enables a gradual shift

in police work from reactive to increasingly proactive approaches, from post-delict to pre-delict action, and from the suppression of security threats towards their prevention.

The Law on Police specifically provides for cooperation with bodies of territorial autonomy, local self-government, public institutions, non-governmental and other organizations, minority and organized groups, and self-organized citizens, with the aim of ensuring the safety of people and property and developing partnerships in the prevention and detection of criminal offences and their perpetrators (Law on Police, 2018).

5.1. Past Development and Gained Experience

The introduction and development of the community policing model in the Republic of Serbia have been conditioned and enabled by contemporary social changes and trends aimed at strengthening the institutions of a democratic society in Serbia during the late past and the beginning of this century. In this context, since 2001 *RS MOI* has been carrying out preparations for the introduction of the community policing model and has undertaken a number of measures in the reform of preventive police work, the strengthening of legality in police operations, the protection of human and minority rights of citizens, the improvement of communication with the public, and the enhancement of cooperation with citizens and the community. These efforts have created prerequisites for more effective prevention and the development of partnership relations with citizens. The past development of community policing in Serbia included pilot projects and cooperation with international organizations such as the OSCE, DFID, the Norwegian Police Directorate, and local NGOs. Key activities encompassed community surveys, expert consultations, professional training, door-to-door outreach programs, cooperation with the media, advisory bodies, and preventive campaigns (Bošković & Simić, 2004; Nikač, 2019).

With a view to the strategic reform of the police, from 2002 to 2003 *the RS MOI*, in cooperation with the OSCE Mission in the Republic of Serbia, the Danish Center for Human Rights, and recognised international and domestic experts in the field of justice and policing, prepared the official document *Vision for the Reform of RS MOI*, which includes the vision, values, mission, and key areas of work. Recent evaluations of community policing in Serbia highlight the importance of citizen feedback, local adaptation of programs, and continuous monitoring in order to improve effectiveness and trust (Novaković & Ilić, 2020). Studies from other national contexts also emphasize organizational challenges, such as police officer burnout and resource constraints, which affect the sustainability of community policing initiatives (Okoka & Kheswa, 2025). The document defined the purpose of community policing, its objectives, strategic directions of development, tasks, success criteria, and indicators related to communication and trust between the police and the community, education of police officers and community representatives, citizen involvement, partnership between the police and the community, and problem-oriented police work in solving security issues. Particular importance in the planning and implementation of the new concept of police organization and work was also attributed to rich international experience, especially that of developed countries with a strong democratic tradition (Nikač, 2019).

The development of the concept of community policing in Serbia took place in phases, initially covering pilot areas and subsequently expanding to the entire territory of the Republic. Activities carried out in the pilot areas resulted in examples of good practice, which were documented in an evaluation report conducted in December 2004 by representatives of the *RS MOI*, the Department of International Development of the British Government (DFID), and the Police Academy in Belgrade. Based on the experience gained

and identified good practices, further activities were undertaken and continue to be implemented throughout the Republic. To date, the development of community policing in the Republic of Serbia has been accompanied by successful international cooperation with the OSCE Mission in Serbia, the Department of International Development of the British Government (DFID), the National Police Director of the Kingdom of Norway, the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation, and other international partners.

Among the more significant activities is the research project entitled “Police Observation in Serbia”, jointly organized by the *RS MOI*, the OSCE Mission in the Republic of Serbia, and the agency “Partner,” with the aim of gaining insight into citizens’ attitudes, opinions, and expectations regarding security issues, the police as an institution, and its role in the community. The OSCE Mission in the Republic of Serbia also conducted a survey of police officers’ opinions concerning the implementation of community policing.

Numerous expert meetings – courses, seminars, workshops, round tables, and conferences – have been organized in various areas, including modern standards of police work, human rights, strategic management, analysis, and problem-oriented policing. Their aim has been to raise awareness among police officers about contemporary policing practices and the necessity of community participation in improving security.

Education is ongoing through mandatory annual professional training programs for police officers, within which topics related to the theoretical and practical aspects of community policing are addressed. Education of citizens and other community stakeholders on security-related phenomena is conducted through participation in public forums and lectures addressing current issues such as student safety in schools, domestic violence, juvenile delinquency, drug addiction, traffic safety, etc.

Among other activities, it should be noted that consultative meetings are held in local communities at various levels (municipal communities, neighborhoods, streets, residential buildings, and associations) with the aim of improving communication with citizens. “Door-to-door” activities are also carried out, through which police officers communicate directly with citizens regarding their personal safety and security protection. Cooperation with the media has been enhanced through various forms of communication, such as round tables with media representatives, media support through the promotion of community police activities, participation in TV and radio programs, and the creation of audio and video materials for journalists.

The public and citizens are informed (through brochures, flyers, information leaflets, posters, etc.) about their rights and obligations, ways of establishing and improving contact between citizens and the police, procedures for filing complaints regarding police work, traffic safety, protection of property, and other security-related issues (Nikač, 2019). Advisory bodies have been established at the level of local communities in order to involve various stakeholders in addressing security problems. These include safety councils and committees for traffic safety, disease prevention, prevention of juvenile delinquency, safety of children in schools, anti-corruption teams, and similar bodies. In addition to identifying key security problems within the community, these bodies have implemented numerous projects, programs, and actions aimed at improving overall security, with particular emphasis on preventive activities. Furthermore, the work of citizen advisory groups operating at the local community level – whose primary function is to facilitate communication between citizens, the police, and other community actors – has been initiated.

Among other regular activities, particular attention should be given to the project aimed at further developing the methodology of problem-oriented policing, implemented in

cooperation with the National Police Directorate of the Kingdom of Norway. This project encompassed several stages in addressing security problems: problem identification, problem analysis, implementation of measures targeting individuals, situation, and the local community, as well as evaluation of results and processes. Improved cooperation with non-governmental organizations has also been achieved, particularly with organizations addressing domestic violence, along with participation in preventive campaigns, educational activities and the development of partnerships with other relevant actors.

Among the significant initiatives is the “School Police Officer” project, under which, based on security assessments, police officers are deployed in schools with pronounced security challenges. Police officers act preventively in cooperation with schools and other community stakeholders, with a focus on continuous education of police officers, teaching staff, parents, and students on various aspects of student and school safety. In order to enable the police in the Republic of Serbia to operate responsibly and in partnership with the community and citizens, the Community Policing Strategy in the Republic of Serbia was developed as an appropriate framework for police action in the community, adapted to the security and other needs of citizens in Serbia (Bošković & Simić, 2004).

The Strategy is aligned with the National Program for the Integration of the Republic of Serbia into the European Union and provides guidance for establishing and developing new forms of cooperation between the police, citizens, communities, and institutions, with the aim of enhancing personal and collective security in the Republic of Serbia. In this regard, the Strategy represents a continuation of the *MOI* Development Strategy, supports relevant guidelines from the National Security Strategy, and complements other strategies addressing serious security challenges, risks, and threats.

CONCLUSION

Contemporary security challenges of the 21st century have exposed the limitations of the traditional, centralized, and predominantly repressive model of policing, which has proven insufficient both in crime prevention and in building trust between the police and the community. In response to these challenges, the concept of community policing has emerged as the dominant philosophy of modern and democratic police work, based on partnership, prevention, and respect for human rights (Cordner, 2021; Lum & Koper, 2020).

The analysis presented in this paper confirms that community policing represents the most appropriate organizational and value-based framework for police functioning in contemporary democratic societies. This concept does not merely entail changes in operational policing methods, but requires a fundamental transformation of police culture, the role of police officers, and the relationship between the police and citizens as recipients of public services. Particular importance is placed on preventive action, decentralization of certain police functions, and continuous cooperation with the local community.

In the Republic of Serbia, community policing has been adopted as a modern model of police organization and practice, consistent with international standards and European values. The starting point of this concept is the understanding of the police as a public service whose primary role is the protection of societal interests, the rule of law, human and minority rights, civil liberties, equality, and multicultural coexistence. The continued development of the Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Serbia as a modern, professional, and accountable institution represents a key prerequisite for the effective implementation of this model in practice.

Although the subject of this paper is predominantly conceptual and organizational in nature, several *de lege ferenda* recommendations may be identified based on the presented findings. In this regard, it is necessary to further improve the normative framework through the simplification of police-legal procedures and the harmonization of police legislation and by-laws with the legal *acquis* of the European Union. Additionally, the continuous strengthening of professional capacities of police officers, enhancement of mechanisms for cooperation with the local community, and development of effective instruments of police transparency and accountability remain essential (Skogan & Hartnett, 2021; Weisburd et al., 2019). **These findings provide clear guidance for future legislative, organizational, and policy reforms of policing in the Republic of Serbia, particularly in the context of strengthening community policing in accordance with European and international standards.**

In conclusion, community policing should be understood not only as an organizational model, but also as a normative and value-based framework that enables more effective, legitimate, and socially responsible police work. Its consistent implementation contributes to strengthening public security, the rule of law, and citizens' trust in the police, which represents one of the fundamental objectives of contemporary policing systems.

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